

Studies on Complex Compounds of Cobalt(III) with Substituted Thiosemicarbazides : Part-1.

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Four complex compounds of Co(III) of the Formula $[CoL_3]$ with *p*-substituted benzaldehyde thiosemicarbazone (L), *p*-(X).C₆H₄.CH : N.NH.CS.NH₂ (X=NO₂, Cl, NH₂ and OCH₃) have been prepared and characterised. The structures of these complexes have been established on the basis of their elemental analyses, ir, uv and magnetic susceptibility values. All these complexes are diamagnetic and octahedral.

THE earliest and best known six co-ordinated amine complex of Co(III) was first discovered by Tassaert¹ in 1798 when Cobalt Chloride was treated with ammonia. After that numerous complexes of Co(III) with different types of ligands²⁻⁶ were reported but no mention has been made of the formation of Co(III) complexes with substituted thiosemicarbazides.

Herein is reported four Co(III) complexes, namely, tris *p*-nitrobenzaldehydethiosemicarbazone Co(III), tris *p*-chlorobenzaldehydethiosemicarbazone Co(III), tris *p*-aminobenzaldehydethiosemicarbazone Co(III) and tris *p*-methoxybenzaldehydethiosemicarbazone Co(III) of the formula $[Co(C_8H_7N_4O_2S)_3]$; $[Co(C_8H_7N_4S)_3]$; $[Co(C_8H_9N_4S)_3]$ and $[Co(C_9H_{10}N_4OS)_3]$ respectively.

Experimental

Ligands :

p-Nitrobenzaldehydethiosemicarbazone was prepared by dissolving 1 gm. *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde in acetone and treated with a solution of thiosemicarbazide hydrochloride in equimolecular quantity in distilled water. Yellow precipitate was obtained when shaken vigorously but by the same process a pale yellow precipitate of *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde thiosemicarbazone was obtained when shaken only for a few minutes.

In the case of *p*-aminobenzaldehydethiosemicarbazone a liquid layer was obtained after refluxing on water bath for about an hour, the liquid layer extracted with ether and solidified by distilling off ether.

But the heavy liquid layer obtained in the case of *p*-methoxybenzaldehydethiosemicarbazone was separated by means of a separating funnel and solidified by evaporation on a water bath.

Cobaltic Nitrate :

2.5 gms. of $Co(NO_3)_2$ was dissolved in about 250 c.c. distilled water and oxidised by blowing air through it till deep red colour of Cobaltic nitrate solution was obtained. This solution containing 3.34 gms of Cobaltic nitrate was diluted to 334 c.c. for one p.c. solution of Cobaltic nitrate. This solution was used for the preparation of Co(III) complexes.

Complexes :

For the preparation of these complexes 10 c.c. of one p.c. solution of Cobaltic nitrate was treated with the ligand solution prepared by dissolving equimolecular quantity of the ligand in acetone, refluxed on water bath for about 20 minutes, cooled to room temperature and then made alkaline by adding a very dilute solution of ammonia. After leaving the solution for some hours fine crystals were obtained, filtered, washed with cold water containing a little ammonia and dried in air.

Results and Discussion

All the four Co(III) complexes were soluble in acetone but insoluble in benzene, ethyl alcohol, methyl alcohol and chloroform.

Some of their important properties are given below in Table-1.

Compounds	1 Colour	2 Co		3 N		4 C		5 H	
		Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
$[Co(C_8H_7N_4O_2S)_3]$	Deep red	8.08	8.09	22.08	23.07	39.36	39.56	2.81	2.90
$[Co(C_8H_7N_4ClS)_3]$	Deep brown	8.44	8.45	18.02	18.08	41.20	41.35	3.01	3.03
$[Co(C_8H_9N_4S)_3]$	Brown	9.20	9.22	26.11	26.31	45.00	45.13	4.20	4.26
$[Co(C_9H_{10}N_4OS)_3]$	Deep brown	8.60	8.62	18.30	18.43	47.04	47.23	4.20	4.39

Infra red spectra :

exhibited two bands in the ir spectra (nujol mull) at 1350 cm^{-1} and 1680 cm^{-1} which corresponded to characteristic groups $\text{C}=\text{S}$ and $\text{C}=\text{N}$. The peaks observed around $1300\text{--}1330\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $1650\text{--}1670\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the ir spectra of the complexes corresponded to characteristic groups $\text{C}=\text{S}$ and $\text{C}=\text{N}$ and are indicative of the bidentate nature of the ligand and the co-ordination takes place through sulphur and nitrogen.

Ultra-Violet spectra :

From the Orgel diagram of various d^8 systems it is clear that the splitting of the state is a function of D_4 for octahedral complexes with electronic configuration d^1 and d^8 (term symbol 3D). The spectra of these complexes contain only one band arising from d-d transition and this is assigned as $T_{2g}-E_g$.

In the case of high-spin diamagnetic octahedral complexes⁷ strong band appears in the orange and red part of the visible spectrum. Hence the electronic absorption spectral measurement of Co(III) complexes in acetone solution showed the maximum peak between $600\text{--}630\text{ m}\mu$ which is indicative of the octahedral structure.

Magnetic susceptibility :

The measurement of magnetic susceptibility (Found $\mu_B=0.0\text{ BM}$, expected $\mu_B=0.0\text{ BM}$) by Gouy's method indicated that the complexes are diamagnetic and octahedral.

Structure of thiosemicarbazone complexes :

Various metallic complexes of organic sulphur compounds have been described in the literature⁸⁻¹⁰. Some years back, B.A. Gingras¹⁴ and others have studied several copper complexes and have suggested that co-ordination with thiosemicarbazone takes place through sulphur and nitrogen atoms.

Jensen prepared several substituted thiosemicarbazides and found that neither in alkaline nor in acidic media did substituted thiosemicarbazides form complexes ; indicating the necessity of metal , sulphur bonding. He also concluded that co-ordination in M(II) -thiosemicarbazide and M(II) -semicarbazide complex is through the N^1 atom¹⁵. He arrived at this conclusion from the observation that 1-arylthio-

semicarbazide, $(\text{Ar}-\overset{1}{\text{NH}}-\overset{2}{\text{NH}}-\overset{3}{\text{CS}}-\overset{4}{\text{NH}_2})$ did not form

Nickel(II) complexes and 1-acyl $(\text{RCONH}-\overset{1}{\text{NH}}-\overset{2}{\text{NH}}-\overset{3}{\text{CS}}-\overset{4}{\text{NH}_2})$, 1,1-disubstituted thiosemicarbazides $(\text{R}_1\text{R}_2\text{N}-$

$\overset{2}{\text{NH}}-\overset{3}{\text{CS}}-\overset{4}{\text{NH}_2})$ gave no copper(II) complexes in acidic media.

That the co-ordination through sulphur and N^1 takes place has also been supported by T.A. Preobrazhenskaya¹⁶.

Thus on the basis of above measurements and arguments the expected structure is represented as

where $\text{X}=\text{NO}_2, \text{Cl}, \text{NH}_2$ and OCH_3 .

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